

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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ECONOMETRIC ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECT OF INVESTMENTS ON THE VOLUME OF CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTION

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Abstract. In this article, a regression analysis of the impact of investments on the volume of construction production was carried out. Conclusions about short-term and long-term changes were made by creating an autoregression model.

Key words: model, autoregression, regression equation, Student t test, Fisher, instrumental variable.

In order to assess the impact of investments on the volume of construction production of Surkhondarya region, data for 2010-2023 were obtained from www.surkhonstat.uz (Table 1).

Table 1

Construction production and investment volume indicators of Surkhondarya region¹

<i>Year</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>x</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>x</i>
2010	335,9	655,3	2017	1 827,0	3 551,0
2011	470,6	802,9	2018	2 879,7	7 240,6
2012	605,3	980,3	2019	3 979,7	11 835,1
2013	849,5	1 371,0	2020	4 774,7	10 068,2
2014	1 051,5	1 509,1	2021	5 868,4	12 037,8
2015	1 351,3	1 843,6	2022	6 521,9	11 569,4
2016	1 554,8	2 142,4	2023	7 353,3	17 956,0

Autoregression models are useful in assessing the short-term and long-term impact of investments on the volume of construction production. The general appearance of the $AR(1) + x$ model is as follows:

$$y_t = a + b_0 \cdot x_t + c_1 \cdot y_{t-1} + e_t \quad (1)$$

To calculate model (1), it is necessary to first create a model that evaluates the instrumental variable:

¹ Information from the Surkhondarya Region Statistics Department website www.surkhonstat.uz

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$$\hat{y}_{t-1} = d_0 + d_1 \cdot x_{t-1} \quad (2)$$

To estimate the model (2), we need to determine the lags of the y_t and factor indicators for the period t-1 (Table 2).

Table 2

Values of the indicators of the volume of construction production and investments in fixed capital of Surkhandarya region in the period $t - 1^2$

Year	y_t	x_t	y_{t-1}	x_{t-1}
2010	335,9	655,3	-	-
2011	470,6	802,9	335,9	655,3
2012	605,3	980,3	470,6	802,9
2013	849,5	1 371,0	605,3	980,3
2014	1 051,5	1 509,1	849,5	1 371,0
2015	1 351,3	1 843,6	1 051,5	1 509,1
2016	1 554,8	2 142,4	1 351,3	1 843,6
2017	1 827,0	3 551,0	1 554,8	2 142,4
2018	2 879,7	7 240,6	1 827,0	3 551,0
2019	3 979,7	11 835,1	2 879,7	7 240,6
2020	4 774,7	10 068,2	3 979,7	11 835,1
2021	5 868,4	12 037,8	4 774,7	10 068,2
2022	6 521,9	11 569,4	5 868,4	12 037,8
2023	7 353,3	17 956,0	6 521,9	11 569,4

Using the OLS method in the Gretl program, we estimate the form of association of the lag indicators in Table 2 (Table 3).

Table 3

Results of regression analysis³

Model 2: OLS, using observations 2011-2023 (T = 13)

Dependent variable: yt1

Coefficient *Std. Error* *t-ratio* *p-value*

² Information from the Surkhandarya Region Statistics Department website www.surkhonstat.uz

³ Development of the author

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xt-1	0.464409	0.0256488	18.11	<0.0001	***
Mean dependent var	2466.947	S.D. dependent var		2138.834	
Sum squared resid	4731975	S.E. of regression		627.9580	
Uncentered squared	R- 0.964690	Centered squared	R-	0.913800	
F(1, 12)	327.8440	P-value(F)		4.44e-10	
Log-likelihood	-101.6781	Akaike criterion		205.3562	
Schwarz criterion	205.9211	Hannan-Quinn		205.2400	
rho	0.444907	Durbin-Watson		1.079236	

From Table 3, the general view of the regression equation of the instrumental variable \hat{y}_{t-1} is as follows:

$$\hat{y}_{t-1} = 0,464409 \cdot x_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

The calculated value of Fisher's F criterion is equal to $F_{est} = 327,844$ 4. This value is greater than Fisher's table value $F_{1,12;0,05} = 4.75$ at $\alpha = 0,05$ significance level. Also, the value of the Student's t criterion are equal to $t_{d_1} = 18,1$, which is greater than the table value of the Student's t criterion $t_{13;0,05} = 2,16$ at the degree of freedom $df = n - m = 13$. Therefore, the model is statistically significant.

We determine the theoretical values of the instrumental variable \hat{y}_{t-1} . (Table 4).

Table 4

Theoretical values of the instrumental variable⁴

Year	y_t	x_t	y_{t-1}	x_{t-1}	\hat{y}_{t-1}
2010	335,9	655,3	-	-	-
2011	470,6	802,9	335,9	655,3	304,3

⁴ Information from the Surkhandarya Region Statistics Department website www.surkhonstat.uz

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2012	605,3	980,3	470,6	802,9	372,9
2013	849,5	1 371,0	605,3	980,3	455,3
2014	1 051,5	1 509,1	849,5	1 371,0	636,7
2015	1 351,3	1 843,6	1 051,5	1 509,1	700,9
2016	1 554,8	2 142,4	1 351,3	1 843,6	856,2
2017	1 827,0	3 551,0	1 554,8	2 142,4	995,0
2018	2 879,7	7 240,6	1 827,0	3 551,0	1 649,1
2019	3 979,7	11 835,1	2 879,7	7 240,6	3 362,6
2020	4 774,7	10 068,2	3 979,7	11 835,1	5 496,3
2021	5 868,4	12 037,8	4 774,7	10 068,2	4 675,8
2022	6 521,9	11 569,4	5 868,4	12 037,8	5 590,4
2023	7 353,3	17 956,0	6 521,9	11 569,4	5 372,9

It is possible to evaluate the model (1) with the participation of variables y_t , x_t and \hat{y}_{t-1} in Table 4. For this, we again used Gretl's capabilities. (Table 5).

Table 5

Results of regression analysis⁵

Model 2: OLS, using observations 2011-2023 (T = 13)

Dependent variable: y

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-ratio</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
const	346.814	187.231	1.852	0.0937	*
x	0.216391	0.0574790	3.765	0.0037	***
yt-1_fitted	0.546096	0.149724	3.647	0.0045	***
Mean dependent var	3006.744	S.D. dependent var	2422.853		
Sum squared resid	1933064	S.E. of regression	439.6662		
R-squared	0.972558	Adjusted R-squared	0.967070		
F(2, 10)	177.2045	P-value(F)	1.56e-08		
Log-likelihood	-95.85904	Akaike criterion	197.7181		
Schwarz criterion	199.4129	Hannan-Quinn	197.3697		

⁵ Development of the author

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rho 0.399093 Durbin-Watson 1.173993

Test for normality of residual -

Null hypothesis: error is normally distributed

Test statistic: Chi-square(2) = 1.99324

with p-value = 0.369125

Based on Table 3, autoregression equation has the following general form:

$$y_t = 346,814 + 0,216391x_t + 0,546096y_{t-1} \quad (4)$$

It can be seen from the model (4) that the short-term multiplier is equal to $b_0 = 0,216391$, and the long-term multiplier is equal to $b = \frac{b_0}{1-c} = \frac{0,216391}{1-0,546096} = 0,476733$

In conclusion, an increase in the volume of investments in fixed capital by 1 billion soums increases the volume of construction production by an average of 0.216391 billion soums. An increase of x_t by 1 billion soums increases y_t by 0.546096 billion soums in the long term.

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